

ADVANCES IN INTERACTIVE PROCESSING AND VISUALISATION WITH JUPYTERLAB ON THE JRC BIG DATA PLATFORM (JEODPP)

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ABSTRACT

The JRC Big Data Platform (JEODPP) is serving JRC projects and their partners for any big data application with emphasis on geospatial data. It has recently evolved into a multi-petabyte scale platform offering advanced web enabled services for container-based batch processing, remote desktop, and interactive analysis and visualization. This later service, based on Jupyter, has recently unfolded into a complete and powerful prototyping environment. This paper describes the most significant advances in this area.

Index Terms— deferred processing, Sentinel, Copernicus, visualisation, Jupyter, JupyterLab, IPython

1. INTRODUCTION

The results presented in this paper are implemented on the JRC Big Data Platform (JEODPP) [4]. This platform serves the needs of JRC policy support activities requiring big data capabilities with emphasis on geospatial data as well as any data sources associated with a geolocation (news articles, official statistics, pictures, etc.). The platform is implemented on a commodity hardware solution scalable to the multi-petabyte scale. This is achieved through distributed storage (CERN EOS) coupled with a cluster of computing nodes for distributed computing. The JEODPP platform can be viewed as a three layer pyramid with a multi-petabyte scale storage and processing basis. The first layer accommodates massive batch processing. The second layer provides a remote desktop environment with all software needed for further developing legacy applications. The tip of the pyramid (third layer) provides interactive visualization and analysis in a web-based environment integrated in a Jupyter notebook [1].

This paper concentrates on the advances regarding the interactive analysis and visualization layer. The following aspects are detailed: evolution from Jupyter to JupyterLab, availability of new data collections, the possibility to execute arbitrary Python code, and applications for users without programming capabilities exploiting the temporal dimension of geospatial data cubes.

2. FROM JUPYTER TO JUPYTERLAB

JupyterLab¹ is an evolution of Jupyter released to users in February 2018. It provides a series of features improving the user-experience such as the use text editors, terminals, data file viewers, and other custom components side by side with notebooks in a tabbed work area [2]. In particular, it gives the possibility to redirect the map view area in a side map.

3. DATA COLLECTIONS

Since its inception, the JEODPP platform has been characterized by providing users with a wide variety of raster and vector geospatial datasets. Complex raster collections such as those originating from the Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 satellites are available alongside continental or global open-source DEMs (EU-DEM, SRTM, GEBCO, MERIT, etc.). They can be interactively visualised together with vector datasets such as NATURA2000, EFFIS forest fires, administrative territorial units, and land use-land cover at European level (Corine Land Cover and Urban Atlas). New datasets are continuously integrated in the interactive mode. This is for instance the case of the new global DEM at a resolution of 30 meters produced by the Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA) and called "ALOS World 3D AW3D30" [6]. The deferred mode processing functions of the JEODPP APIs allow to obtain high-impact visualizations such as that presented in Fig. 1 displaying the coloured hill-shading of the ALOS DEM with a custom colour scheme.

Other dataset recently made available in the interactive mode are the Sentinel-1 global mosaic [5], and a cloud-free Sentinel-2 global mosaic calculated from images acquired in 2017 [3]. No less important is the availability of many basemaps that can be used as background of views and ranging from the classic OpenStreetMap, OpenTopoMap, up to MODIS data with daily granularity, high resolution aerial images, maps in neutral colors that better enhance the geographic content superimposed on them. The selection of the basemap to use or of the dataset to be displayed, takes place in a very simple way that allows the user to view the datasets

¹JupyterLab: <https://jupyterlab.readthedocs.io>

Fig. 1: ALOS Global Digital Surface Model "ALOS World 3D 30m (AW3D30)" rendered on-the-fly on the JEODPP with a colored hill-shading whose parameters are user-defined.

available in a tree structure, easily navigable and searchable using keywords as well as the self-completion functions available in the Python language. Finally, place names originating from CartoDB² can be overlaid on the displayed layer.

4. EMBEDDING PYTHON CODE IN THE TILE ENGINE

At the base of the interactive component of JEODPP there is a library developed in C++ language that represents the real heart of the Tile Engine, a highly parallelized component that creates in real-time and in deferred mode, the raster tiles to send to the visualization based on the ipyleaflet widget³.

After selecting the datasets to be displayed, processing chains transforming and processing the input data in order to extract the desired information are defined. The basic elements of these chains are a series of processing steps that have been implemented within the Tile Engine through the integration of open source processing libraries or libraries developed over the years at the JRC. These libraries (mialib and pktools, among others) provide the main functions necessary for the processing of geographical data and allow for the creation of complex processing chains based on morphological operators, image classification and segmentation functions, band arithmetic, and image filtering in space and time.

Although the list of processing steps is rather extensive and comprehensive, the need has emerged for adding user-defined functions. In a language like Python, dozens of very efficient libraries manipulating images are available (e.g., Numpy, Scipy nd-image, Scikit-image, Python Imaging Library, and OpenCV). By adding a special processing step, called execute, which allows the user to send to the Tile Engine that operates server-side, any function written in Python and that could potentially use such libraries.

²CartoDB: <https://carto.com>

³Ipyleaflet: <https://github.com/jupyter-widgets/ipyleaflet>

Stubble burning detection for Sentinel2:

```
B04 < 1000 AND
B06 < 1200 AND
B08 < 1200 AND
B11 > 500 AND
B11 < 1600
```

Function definition that implements the stubble burning algorithm:

```
def stubble(v4, v6, v8, v11min, v11max):
    global img
    img = numpy.ones_like(band0)
    img[band0>=v4] = 0
    img[band1>=v6] = 0
    img[band2>=v8] = 0
    img[numpy.logical_or(band3<=v11min,
                        band3>=v11max)] = 0
```

Multi-band processing chain containing the python function call:

```
bands = ["B04", "B06", "B08", "B11"]
p = coll.processMulti(bands)
    .execute(stubble, 1000, 1200, 1200, 500, 1600)
    .band(0).scale(0,1).colorCustom(["lime"])
```

Fig. 2: (Top left) Informal description of the Stubble Burning detection algorithm. (Top right) Python implementation of the algorithm using Numpy methods. (Bottom) Multi-band processing chain containing the execute step calling the custom Python function.

Thanks to the Python inspect module, the source lines of the user function are read and sent to the C++ Tile Engine server, where a Python on-the-fly interpreter is instantiated. The code is then executed within the interpreter at each tile request. The function can freely modify the input image pixels to pass them to the next step of the processing chain.

As an example, in Fig. 2, an application of the execute processing chain to the detection of stubble burning (the deliberate setting fire of the straw stubble that remains after wheat and other grains have been harvested) from Sentinel-2 images, based on a simple algorithm that takes as inputs the bands B04, B06, B08 and B11 (Short Wave Infra Red band).

This new development is opening many new scenarios to the JEODPP users that gain a completely new flexibility in the analysis and processing of geospatial datasets. Moreover, it will allow, in the near future, to also take benefit from the many Machine Learning libraries available in Python that could be injected inside the server-side processing chain to extract valuable information from EO data using artificial intelligence techniques.

4.1. Widget enabled applications

Researchers or scientists who possess programming capabilities can easily get into using python to interact with the viewing and analysis environment within Jupyter notebooks. Despite this, the need has emerged to create simpler tools that would allow to work with geographic datasets through a graphical user interface. This is even more true for the manager level users and policy officers having no or very little programming knowledge. For these users, an interface exploiting the analysis/viewing capabilities without the need to write code is needed. Within the Jupyter world, this can be effectively and efficiently enabled by using the ipy-

Fig. 3: S2-Explorer notebook in action. Loading of a custom vector shapefile on the map, search of the Sentinel-2 products that cover it and filtering on cloud cover percentage.

widgets suite⁴ for the creation of user interfaces and on the use of components such as Bqplot⁵ for charting functions and Qgrid⁶ for displaying alphanumeric data in rows with intuitive scrolling, sorting, and filtering controls.

The first fully fledged application implemented, called the S2-Explorer, is devoted to easy browsing and searching of Sentinel-2 products. It consists of a tabbed interface containing many functions going from searching of products covering the current view extents, displaying one or multiple products on the map, selecting between many possible RGB bands compositions, apply local stretching to the products visualization, and filtering of the searched products on multiple criteria (for instance on cloud cover or product type or acquisition dates, etc.). Input capabilities allow the users of S2-Explorer to easily add a custom vector shapefile to the map, and use it to select the Sentinel products covering its features. Many export functions are available, e.g. export the list of the selected Sentinel-2 products to be used for batch processing operations, export of the map view in high resolution TIFF file, creation of an animation video that displays one after the other all the filtered products. The measure and draw tabs can be used to measure distances and areas on the map and the creation of vector features with the possibility to save them in a vector format. Figure 3 shows a snapshot of the S2-Explorer in action.

5. EXPLOITING THE TEMPORAL DIMENSION

The Copernicus constellation of EO satellites is characterized by the high temporal resolution of its acquisitions. As an example, after the launch of Sentinel-2B satellite, all emerged lands will be covered by a new optical product at least ev-

⁴ipywidgets: <https://ipywidgets.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

⁵Bqplot: <https://github.com/bloomberg/bqplot>

⁶Qgrid: <https://qgrid.readthedocs.io/en/latest>

Fig. 4: Extraction of the multi-temporal NDVI profile over the pixels inside a polygon by the S2-Explorer tool.

ery five days. This gives space to many applications where the exploitation of the short revisit time allows for important analytical results, whether for the agricultural, the forest, or disaster monitoring applications. The JEODPP S2-Explorer leverages on the temporal dimension of Sentinel products by providing a series of analysis tools based on multi-temporal data.

5.1. Temporal profiles

One of the tabs of the S2-Explorer tools is dedicated to the extraction of multi-temporal information over the pixels covered by polygonal features. After having searched and filtered the Sentinel-2 products, users can ask the system to calculate, for each of the products, the mean value of an index (e.g., NDVI, EVI, or SAVI) or of a band, together with their standard deviation and plot both values on a temporal graph where the line series represent the mean value inside the polygon and the vertical bars the homogeneity measured by the standard deviation (see Fig. 4). This function has many applications and can be activated also on a custom edited polygon. It has to be noted that the extraction is done server-side on the highly parallel cluster and gives the results in few seconds even in case of dozens or hundreds of input products. Once the desired measurement is determined, it can be scaled to datasets of any size via the batch processing service.

5.2. Easy comparison using the split map control

The ability to easily compare two different views of the same area, whether based on two different datasets or on two different processing chains applied to the same data, is a fundamental capability of any geospatial data viewer. It can be used for comparing two complementary datasets (like a DEM and a EO image, or a basemap and a vector dataset, etc.) or two

Fig. 5: Temporal comparison of two SWIR RGB compositions, from Sentinel-2 images acquired before and after the 2018 Mati fires in Greece.

Fig. 6: Video overlay of a georeferenced temporal video showing one after the other all the Sentinel-2 images acquired over an area within a selected time period.

acquisition dates from the same sensor. This is implemented thanks to a new function available on ipyleaflet: the split map control. When activated, the tool displays a vertical line at the center of the map and the two datasets on each side of the line. The user can move the line horizontally to quickly compare the left and right map on the same geographic area. This is illustrated in Fig. 5 in the case of forest fires by comparing the last Sentinel-2 product acquired before the event with the first acquired after it.

5.3. Georeferenced temporal video

Recent versions of ipyleaflet allow for the overlay of videos on top of the map. We are using this new function to create georeferenced videos starting from the multi-temporal Sentinel-2 products acquired over the same area. The videos can be played directly over the map (even while zooming and panning) and give an interesting insight on the evolution of the land over time with possible application in agriculture (like the evaluation of harvesting times) or in forest monitoring (e.g. control of illegal deforestation activities).

6. OUTLOOK

Batch processing and remote desktop capabilities are fundamental to any platform aiming at extracting insights from massive datasets. Interactive analysis and visualization are also essential to leverage on the increasing number and diversity of the available datasets. They help users to discover new datasets and combine them for prototyping new information extraction workflows. In this respect, the possibility to execute arbitrary code opens an avenue for countless possibilities and in particular has unfolded the interactive analysis and visualisation layer into a complete and powerful prototyping environment. In addition, the code used in the interactive mode is decoupled from the complexity of the visualisation engine so that it can be directly used for batch processing for which precise analysis can be performed in any desired projection. On the other hand, higher level interfaces based on widgets are increasing the outreach and impact of geospatial data by attracting users with no programming skills. Future developments of the JRC Big Data Platform include the integration of machine learning in all layers of the platform while expanding the variety of the available datasets including those not related directly to geospatial data in support to decision and policy making.

7. REFERENCES

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